

NEWSLETTER

ISSUE 1, MARCH 2023

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1. BIOSYSMO IN BRIEF

BIOSYSMO proposes the formulation and application of a computational model-driven framework for the design and improvement of synergetic biosystems for removal of mixed contaminants from polluted soils, sediments and (ground) water.

BIOSYSMO is a 48-month action that will develop a computationally-assisted framework for designing and optimizing synergistic biosystems combining the required pathways and traits to achieve the most efficient degradation and sequestration of pollutant mixtures.

These biosystems will comprise combinations of bacteria, fungi and plants containing the natural or engineered pathways required for pollutants degradation and identified based on

a computationally-assisted analysis. BIOSYSMO will take advantage of the high natural microbial diversity by screening samples from polluted sites and locations affected by diffuse pollution to identify natural microorganisms already present and able to metabolize the target pollutants. The search will be expanded to microorganisms previously identified and characterized by applying data mining tools to genomic and metagenomic data available in public repositories.

The constructed biosystems will be optimized for the treatment of mixtures of pollutants in soil, sediments and waters through conventional (phytoremediation, biopile, bioaugmentation) and innovative (BES, hybrid BES-phytoremediation) bioremediation approaches.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

BIOSYSMO WEBSITE

The BIOSYSMO website was designed and launched in November 2022.

Navigate through its Concept, Objectives, and Outcomes, meet our multidisciplinary team, familiarise with the project's Workplan, Methodology, Applications, and Field studies and stay up to date visiting our media section, including News, Events, Newsletters & Press Releases deriving from the BIOSYSMO team. Access the D&C material, Publications, and Public deliverables as well as our cluster projects and do not hesitate contacting us for any further information.

Visit our website: www.biosysmo.eu

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

BIOSYSMO COMMUNICATION TOOLBOX

The Dissemination and Communication toolbox already designed and developed under BIOSYSMO can be found in the dedicated section of our website including:

BIOSYSMO TEMPLATES:

- o Presentation Slides
- o Deliverable Template
- o Agenda
- o List of participants
- o Meeting minutes

PRINTED MATERIAL:

- o Brochure
- o Flyer
- o Roll up
- o Poster
- o Folder
- o Badges

Visit our website: www.biosysmo.eu/dc-material

4. ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The BIOSYSMO consortium has already presented their work in several workshops and initiatives.

MicroTechWeek 2022 training

9 Nov 2022

Ljubljana (online)

Find out more: www.microtechweek.com/home

International Days of Women and Girls in Science

6-13 Feb 2023, Burgos

Find out more: www.laestacioncyt.es/formacion/actividades/xii-smc-nosotros-tambien-somos-cientifics/

LEGO Microbes training

29 Sept 2022

Slovenia

4. ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

UPCOMING EVENTS

Our partners

Partner	Event	Year	Date	Location	Logo	Website
UBFC	SETAC conference	2023	30 Apr - 3 May	Dublin		https://europe2023.setac.org
CIIMAR, JSI, UBFC	IMAB23 (International Congress on Metal-microbe applications for circular economy),	2023	19-21 Apr	Porto		https://imab23.ciimar.up.pt
IDE	BioRemid 2023	2023	28-Jun	Muttenz, Switzerland		https://biotech.net.ch/network/event/bioremid2023
UBU	AquaConSoil Conference 2023	2023	11-15 September	Prague (Czech Republic)		https://www.aquaconsoil.com/aquaconsoil-2023
JSI	Trends in Microbial Solutions for Sustainable Agriculture	2023	13 – 15 Sept	Serbia		https://www.icgeb.org/trends-in-microbial-solutions-workshop-serbia-2023
JSI	FEMS Hamburg	2023	9 - 13 July	Hamburg		https://www.fems2023.org
UBFC	ICOBTE/ICHMET	2023	6-10 September	Wuppertal (Germany)		https://icobte-ichmet-2023.com/frontend/index.php?folder_id=5888&page_id

5. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS AND PRESS RELEASES

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Our coordinator Dr Lila Otero from IDENER presented the BIOSYSMO project concept and activities in the framework of **MicroTechWeek 2022** workshop on November 8th. The audience included stakeholders amongst the fields of surface and colloid biology interested in technologies with applications in different industrial sectors.

6. BIOSYSMO PUBLICATION

Two publications are already available in open access journals by Imperial College of London.

BIOSYSMO

Check out our new publication!

Imperial College London

Production of selenium nanoparticles occurs through an interconnected pathway of sulphur metabolism and oxidative stress response in Pseudomonas putida KT2440

Roberta Amabile¹ | Said Abdul-Moneem² | Olga-Rose Collins¹ | Sara Flores-Schmitt^{1,2} | Robert Munnings¹ | Robert Schuster¹ | Rana Vora¹ | Rajat Maiti¹ | Alex C. Johnston¹ | Rana Vora¹ | Juyong Kim¹ | Max Chikara^{1,2}

“Production of selenium nanoparticles occurs through an interconnected pathway of sulphur metabolism and oxidative stress response in Pseudomonas putida KT2440” in Microbial Biotechnology Journal.

BIOSYSMO

New publication by ICL

Imperial College London

ENVIRONMENTAL MICROBIOLOGY

WILEY Applied Microbiology Insights

“Water potential governs the effector specificity of the transcriptional regulator XylR of Pseudomonas putida” in Environmental Microbiology Journal.

7. CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

BIOSYSMO project has kick started clustering activities along with MIBIREM (Horizon Europe), SYMBIOREM (Horizon Europe), NYMPHE (Horizon Europe), ELECTRA (H2020), EiCLaR (H2020) and GREENER (H2020). In the framework of this cluster a common workshop is organised in the framework of the upcoming BioRemid 2023 conference:

Wednesday, 28th of June 2023, 14:00 – 17:00
FHNW Campus Muttetz, Switzerland
Agenda will be announced soon in
the BIOSYSMO website...

www.bioremid.com

**CLICK
HERE
TO CHECK
OUT OUR
CLUSTER!**

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WWW.BIOSYSMO.EU | INFO@BIOSYSMO.EU

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